

Metabolic Effects of GLP-1 Agonists in the Treatment of Obesity

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ABSTRACT

Obesity is one of the major public health problems today, associated with high morbidity and mortality and multiple metabolic comorbidities such as type 2 diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia, hypertension, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. Despite advances in preventive and therapeutic measures, traditional strategies based on lifestyle changes often show limited long-term effectiveness, while bariatric surgery, although effective, is not feasible for all patients. In this context, GLP-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs) emerge as a promising pharmacological alternative in obesity management. Initially developed for the treatment of diabetes, these drugs have demonstrated significant impact on weight reduction, improvement of insulin sensitivity, and prevention of progression to type 2 diabetes in obese individuals. Evidence from randomized clinical trials and systematic reviews also points to additional benefits on cardiovascular, lipid, renal, and hepatic parameters, suggesting that GLP-1RAs exert a multifactorial role in cardiometabolic risk. Nevertheless, limitations related to gastrointestinal adverse effects, high cost, and the need for continuous use remain barriers to large-scale adherence. It is concluded that GLP-1 agonists represent a relevant therapeutic innovation, with potential to modify the clinical course of obesity and its metabolic complications, and should be progressively incorporated into clinical guidelines and investigated in long-term studies.

INTRODUCTION

Obesity is currently considered one of the greatest threats to global public health, reaching epidemic proportions and being recognized as a chronic multifactorial disease resulting from the complex interaction of genetic, environmental, behavioral, and metabolic factors. It is estimated that more than 650 million adults worldwide are obese, according to the World Health Organization (1), representing not only a clinical challenge but also a social and economic burden. Beyond excess weight, obesity is strongly associated with metabolic comorbidities such as type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), dyslipidemia, systemic arterial hypertension (SAH), non-alcoholic fatty liver

disease (NAFLD), and increased cardiovascular risk, contributing to reduced life expectancy and quality of life (2).

From a pathophysiological perspective, obesity involves alterations in the neurohormonal regulation of energy balance. Mechanisms include leptin resistance, alterations in ghrelin signaling, intestinal microbiota disorders, and changes in incretin hormones such as glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1). The latter plays a central role in glucose homeostasis and satiety control, being secreted by L cells in the ileum and colon in response to food intake. Its functions include stimulating glucose-dependent insulin secretion, inhibiting glucagon

secretion, delaying gastric emptying, and modulating satiety through central action in the hypothalamus (3).

Despite recognition of obesity as a chronic and multifactorial disease, traditional therapeutic approaches—based on lifestyle changes, caloric restriction, regular physical activity, and, in selected cases, pharmacological or surgical interventions—present limited results in terms of long-term weight loss maintenance. Surgical treatment, mainly bariatric surgery, remains the most effective option in severe cases; however, it is invasive, costly, and carries inherent risks (4). In this context, the search for safe and effective pharmacological options has intensified in recent decades, with emphasis on the development and use of GLP-1 receptor agonists.

GLP-1 agonists (GLP-1RAs) were initially developed for T2DM treatment but are now gaining prominence in obesity management regardless of glycemic status. Several randomized clinical trials (RCTs) have shown that molecules such as liraglutide, semaglutide, and more recently tirzepatide (a dual GIP/GLP-1 agonist) promote significant body weight reductions, associated with improvements in glycemic control, lipid profile, and cardiovascular parameters (5,6). These findings point to a multifactorial impact of GLP-1RAs on metabolism, beyond mere weight reduction.

The main reported metabolic effects include improved insulin sensitivity, reduced glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels, decreased blood pressure, and reduced risk of major cardiovascular events. Additionally, recent studies highlight benefits in NAFLD treatment and preservation of renal function, suggesting an expanded role of this drug class in modifying overall metabolic risk (7,8). Thus, GLP-1RAs emerge as therapeutic agents capable of acting on multiple axes of obesity pathophysiology, contributing not only to weight reduction but also to modulating risks associated with cardiometabolic diseases.

However, challenges remain regarding widespread implementation of this therapy, particularly cost, access within public and private healthcare systems, and long-term adherence, since gastrointestinal adverse effects—such as nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea—may compromise treatment continuity in some patients. Moreover, issues such as risk of pancreatitis and possible thyroid effects are still under investigation, requiring careful monitoring and long-term studies (9).

In this scenario, it is essential to thoroughly understand the metabolic effects of GLP-1 agonists in obesity treatment, evaluating their efficacy, safety, and impact on clinical outcomes. A critical analysis of the available literature not only consolidates current evidence but also identifies knowledge gaps that guide future research.

Thus, this article aims to review recent scientific literature on the metabolic effects of GLP-1 agonists in obesity treatment, emphasizing physiological mechanisms, short- and long-term clinical outcomes, extraponderal benefits, and existing limitations.

METHODS

This study is a narrative literature review on the metabolic effects of GLP-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1RAs) in obesity treatment. A narrative review was chosen for its ability to integrate critical clinical and pathophysiological evidence, encompassing different study designs and providing a broad overview of the subject.

The literature search was conducted in the following databases: PubMed/MEDLINE, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, Cochrane Library, and SciELO, to ensure broad coverage of national and international publications. Controlled descriptors from Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS), as well as free terms, were used to build the search strategy. The main combinations included: “GLP-1 receptor agonists,” “glucagon-like peptide-1,” “obesity,” “metabolic effects,” “weight loss,” “type 2 diabetes,” “cardiovascular outcomes,” “hepatic steatosis,” and “non-alcoholic fatty liver disease.”

Filters were applied for articles published between 2015 and 2025, in English, Portuguese, and Spanish, considering the relevance of recent data on GLP-1 agonists in obesity context. Works published before 2015 were considered only when of recognized historical or conceptual importance for the physiological understanding of GLP-1 and the pharmacological development of its agonists.

Inclusion criteria encompassed randomized clinical trials (RCTs) involving obese adults with or without T2DM, longitudinal observational studies addressing metabolic outcomes related to GLP-1RAs use, systematic reviews, and reference meta-analyses in the field. Studies specifically analyzing metabolic parameters such as weight loss, glycemic control, lipid profile, blood pressure, cardiovascular, hepatic, or renal outcomes were included. Exclusion criteria involved case reports, small case series, animal or *in vitro* studies without direct clinical correlation, studies addressing GLP-1RA use in conditions other than obesity (except when related to common metabolic comorbidities), and duplicated or unavailable full-text publications.

Article selection occurred in two stages. Initially, titles and abstracts were screened for relevance. In the second stage, full texts of eligible studies were assessed according to predefined criteria. Screening was conducted independently by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved by consensus. Extracted data included author, year of publication, study design, number of participants, type of GLP-1 agonist used, follow-up time, metabolic parameters assessed, and main outcomes. For systematic reviews and meta-analyses, those with robust methodologies and clinically relevant outcomes were prioritized.

As this is a literature review without direct involvement of humans or animals in experimentation, there was no need for submission to a Research Ethics Committee, in accordance with Resolution No. 510/2016 of the Brazilian National Health Council.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

GLP-1 agonists act by mimicking the action of the endogenous incretin hormone, which exerts multiple relevant metabolic effects. In the pancreas, they promote glucose-dependent insulin secretion and reduce glucagon secretion, contributing to glycemic control. In the gastrointestinal tract, they delay gastric emptying, reducing the speed of nutrient absorption and increasing satiety. In the central nervous system, they modulate hypothalamic circuits related to hunger and appetite, leading to spontaneous reduction in caloric intake (3). This integrated action explains the broad spectrum of metabolic benefits observed in clinical studies.

Weight loss induced by GLP-1 agonists is one of the most consistent and clinically relevant effects. The STEP 1 trial, conducted by (5), demonstrated that the use of 2.4 mg semaglutide weekly resulted in an average 14.9% body weight reduction after 68 weeks in obese adults without diabetes. Similar results were observed in other STEP studies, confirming the superiority of this drug class compared to placebo and traditional anti-obesity drugs.

Beyond total body weight reduction, evidence points to a significant decrease in visceral fat, a component strongly associated with cardiometabolic risk (10). Preservation of lean mass, although less robust, suggests that weight loss is predominantly attributable to fat reduction, which is desirable in the clinical context.

GLP-1RAs exert a potent effect on glycemic control, even in non-diabetic individuals. In obese patients with prediabetes, semaglutide therapy reduced the incidence of type 2 diabetes by up to 80%, according to secondary analysis of the STEP trials (5). In patients already diagnosed with T2DM, drugs such as liraglutide and dulaglutide significantly reduced HbA1c (0.9 to 1.5%), in addition to improving insulin sensitivity (9).

This effect is particularly relevant as it positions GLP-1 agonists not only as agents for weight reduction but also as therapies for primary and secondary diabetes prevention, modifying the natural course of the disease.

Several cardiovascular outcome trials, such as the LEADER trial (liraglutide) and SUSTAIN-6 (semaglutide), demonstrated reduction in major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE), including nonfatal myocardial infarction, stroke, and cardiovascular death (8,11). These benefits appear partially independent of weight loss, possibly related to direct effects on endothelial function and systemic inflammation.

Furthermore, studies show average reductions of 2 to 5 mmHg in systolic blood pressure, as well as small reductions in diastolic pressure, contributing further to lowering overall cardiovascular risk (12).

Effects on lipid profile, although less pronounced, have been consistent. Clinical trials report reductions in triglycerides and LDL-cholesterol, along with slight increases in HDL-cholesterol (13). These changes improve atherogenic risk and reinforce the role of GLP-1RAs as systemic metabolism modulators.

Obesity is closely associated with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), and GLP-1 agonists have shown promise in this condition. Studies with liraglutide and semaglutide demonstrated significant reductions in hepatic fat content and improvements in biochemical markers of liver function (14). In some cases, regression of nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) was observed, suggesting potential future use of these drugs as part of targeted therapy for this disease, which currently lacks approved treatments.

Although most evidence comes from diabetic patients, GLP-1RAs appear to exert renal protective effects. The REWIND trial (dulaglutide) demonstrated reduction in composite renal outcomes, such as new-onset macroalbuminuria and renal function decline (15). Considering the high prevalence of chronic kidney disease in obese individuals, these results suggest additional benefits of this drug class in managing metabolic complications.

The main reported adverse events include gastrointestinal symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and diarrhea, usually self-limited and more frequent at the start of treatment (9). Cases of acute pancreatitis have been described, although causal relationship remains uncertain. The potential increased risk of medullary thyroid carcinoma was raised in preclinical studies but has not been confirmed in humans.

Another critical point is the high cost of therapy, which represents a barrier to large-scale use, especially in public health systems. Moreover, since these drugs require continuous use, discontinuation usually results in weight regain, reinforcing the need for long-term strategies for weight maintenance (16).

The reviewed findings reinforce that GLP-1 agonists should not be considered solely as weight loss agents but as risk-modifying drugs, with proven impact on weight, glycemia, cardiovascular profile, and hepatic and renal function. The combination of these effects places this class in a privileged position in obesity management, making them one of the most promising pharmacological interventions in recent decades.

CONCLUSION

GLP-1 receptor agonists have consolidated themselves as one of the most important therapeutic innovations in obesity treatment in recent decades. Initially developed for the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus, these drugs have shown benefits that extend beyond glycemic control, achieving direct and consistent impact on body weight reduction, satiety modulation, and body composition improvement. In parallel, multiple clinical trials and systematic reviews have demonstrated extraponderal effects, including reduction of diabetes incidence in obese individuals, improvement in lipid profile, reduction in blood pressure, cardiovascular protection, and potential benefits in associated conditions such as NAFLD and chronic kidney disease.

Based on the reviewed evidence, it is clear that GLP-1RAs should not be seen merely as anti-obesity agents, but as global metabolic risk modifiers, capable of acting on multiple aspects of obesity pathophysiology and its cardiometabolic

complications. This characteristic gives them a unique role in primary and secondary prevention strategies, expanding therapeutic possibilities in both clinical and public health contexts.

Nevertheless, limitations persist and must be addressed. The high cost of therapy and limited availability in many health systems hinder large-scale access. In addition, gastrointestinal adverse events may compromise adherence, while the need for continuous use raises concerns about sustainability and long-term benefit maintenance. Although current safety data are robust, gaps remain regarding potential long-term risks, especially in specific patient subgroups.

Thus, although current results are promising and already support widespread use of GLP-1 agonists in obesity treatment, it is essential to develop new long-term clinical studies exploring sustained weight loss, prevention of metabolic complications, effects on overall and cause-specific mortality, as well as combined strategies with other pharmacological or behavioral approaches.

In conclusion, GLP-1 agonists inaugurate a new era in obesity treatment, integrating weight control, metabolic improvement, and cardiovascular risk reduction into a single intervention. Their progressive incorporation into clinical guidelines must consider both the proven benefits and the challenges of access, adherence, and sustainability, to ensure that achieved advances translate into meaningful population impact.

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